

Chelating Tendencies of 8-Azaguanine

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Stepwise formation constants of 8-azaguanine (AGN) chelates with the metal ions, Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pb(II) and $UO_2(VI)$ have been evaluated at various ionic strengths employing pH-metric technique at 30° in an aqueous media. Thermodynamic values of the formation constants were obtained by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. The stepwise thermodynamic equilibrium constants are: $K_{H_1} = 10^{10.23}$, $K_{H_2} = 10^{9.46}$ for H^+ ; and $K_1 = 10^{7.93}$, $K_2 = 10^{6.40}$ for Be(II); $K_1 = 10^{10.18}$, $K_2 = 10^{8.06}$, $K_3 = 10^{6.36}$ for Al(III); $K_1 = 10^{9.04}$, $K_2 = 10^{6.86}$ for Cr(III); $K_1 = 10^{8.44}$ for Ni(II); $K_1 = 10^{12.10}$ for Cu(II); $K_1 = 10^{9.70}$ for Pb(II); and $K_1 = 10^{10.18}$ for $UO_2(VI)$ systems.

8-Azaguanine is structurally related to the purine, adenine, thioguanine, 6-mercaptopurine etc., which are less effective as anticancer agents than AGN. The stabilities of its metal chelates are also higher, which have been discussed.

INVESTIGATIONS on the chelation reactions of the anticancer compounds, folic acid¹, riboflavin², adenine³, and thioguanine³, and the carcinogenic compound, 1-amino-2-naphthol³ have already been reported, and their chelating properties, like mode of reactivity and the order of stability constants etc. have been discussed in the light of their anticancer activities. 8-Azaguanine is structurally related to ADN and TGN and is comparatively more effective, but no work appears to have been done on its chelating tendencies. Thus, expecting some relationship between the chelating properties and the anticancer activities, the complexation equilibria of AGN with the carcinogenic metal ions, Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pb(II), $UO_2(VI)$, and the biologically important metal ions Mn(II), Ca(II), Mg(II) have been studied. The experiments were carried out in aqueous media adopting the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-metric technique as used in earlier publications¹⁻³.

Experimental

Materials

Metal nitrate solutions were prepared using aluminium(III), chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), lead(II), uranyl(VI) nitrates; beryllium(II), calcium(II) and magnesium(II) carbonates; and zinc(II) oxide (all BDH AnalaR). Nitrates were dissolved in water and carbonates and oxide were dissolved in known amounts of nitric acid. Metal contents were estimated by usual methods.

1.0M KNO_3 solution was prepared by direct weighing.

0.1016N solution of KOH (BDH AnalaR), was prepared for the titration.

AGN (Koch-Light) was dissolved in known amount of KOH, the final concentration of alkali being 0.01M.

Procedure

The experiments were carried out in aqueous media at 30° employing a Leeds and Northrup pH-meter with a glass-calomel electrode assembly. The titration mixtures: (i) acid HNO_3 ; (ii) 0.001M AGN + mixture (i); (iii) 0.0002M metal nitrate + mixture, (ii) were titrated with the alkali keeping the total volume 50 ml. The ionic strengths were 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10M (KNO_3) as described earlier. From the experimental data, volume of alkali vs. pH, titration curves were plotted and the average number of protons attached per ligand ($\bar{n}_A$), average number of ligands attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$), and the free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated at different pH. Formation curves of the proton-ligand system (curves of pH vs $\bar{n}_A$) and the metal-ligand systems (curves of $\bar{n}$ vs pL) were plotted and the equilibrium constants were evaluated employing the computational methods. The thermodynamic constants were obtained by extrapolating $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves of the acid and the ligand systems show that AGN contains two acidic groups which dissociate in steps like TGN. However there is no information on the protonation of the 2-amino group under the experimental conditions (between pH 3.0 and 11.0). The dissociation of the protons of ligand is shown (see next page).

The ligand solution in the absence of metal ions became turbid below pH 6.7 if it is kept for some time possibly due to the precipitation of the neutral H_2L species. This could be avoided by using freshly prepared solutions and by completing the titrations in as short a time as possible. However, it was not necessary for the studies of equilibria of chelation reactions below pH 5.0, since below this pH the ligand did not dissociate (it remains as H_2L) and the solution was perfectly clear. Thus the chelate

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formation functions below pH 5.0 could be calculated using the acid and the complex curves instead of ligand and the chelate curves.

The formation curves of the protonation system show that the equilibria, $H_2L \rightleftharpoons HL^- + H^+$ and $HL^- \rightleftharpoons L^{2-} + H^+$ independently exist in the pH range between 5.0 and 8.1, and 8.3 and above respectively. The values of the formation constants for these reactions are given in table 1. Protonation constant thus obtained for the amino group is consistent with those for ADN and TGN indicating a close structural relationship.

Chelate formation curves could be obtained only for Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Ni(II), Cu(II), $UO_2(VI)$, and Pb(II) (Figs. are omitted), and the stability constants are given in table 1. The thermodynamic values of the formation constants have been obtained extrapolating to zero ionic strength.

7.6 and 9.8, and only 1 : 1 species is formed in solution below pH 7.6.

A parallel behaviour of a number of complex species formation and the precipitation of the complexing mixture were observed for Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III) chelates with ADN³ and TGN³ and Ni(II) chelate with ADN³. 1 : 1, 1 : 2 metal to ligand species of Cr(III) and 1 : 1 species of Ni(II) are formed in solution. The precipitation for Cr(III)-ADN³, Cr(III)-TGN³ and Ni(II)-ADN² respectively was observed at pH 7.1, 7.5, 8.1.

The maximum $\bar{n}$ values calculated for Cu(II)- and $UO_2(VI)$ -AGN systems are 0.8 and 1.0 respectively before the precipitation of the complex solutions which occurred at pH 4.6 and 6.0 respectively. No such precipitation reaction was observed in ADN chelates with these metal ions. But in the $UO_2(VI)$ -TGN complex mixture turbidity appeared at pH 6.6

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF AGN METAL-CHELATES (30°)

Ionic strength	log K_n^*	H ⁺	Be(II)	Al(III)	Cr(III)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Pb(II)	$UO_2(VI)$
0.10	log K_1	9.90	7.53	9.68	8.63	7.19	10.67	6.24	9.41
	log K_2	6.45	5.80	7.50	6.40	...	...	...	...
	log K_3	...	...	5.90	...	...	...	...	...
0.05	log K_1	9.93	7.55	9.82	8.75	7.56	11.03	6.36	9.63
	log K_2	6.45	5.96	7.67	6.50	...	...	...	...
	log K_3	...	...	6.00	...	...	...	...	...
0.01	log K_1	10.13	7.80	10.00	8.90	7.80	11.63	6.55	9.90
	log K_2	6.45	6.20	7.85	6.70	...	...	...	...
	log K_3	...	...	6.15	...	...	...	...	...
→ 0	log K_1	10.23	7.93	10.18	9.04	8.44	12.10	6.70	10.13
	log K_2	6.45	6.40	8.06	6.86	...	...	...	...
	log K_3	...	...	6.26	...	...	...	...	...

* Range of standard deviation is between ±0.02 and ±0.04.

Be(II) and Al(III) form 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 species respectively in solution. Precipitation was observed above pH 7.0 in the Cr(III) system, and only 1 : 1, 1 : 2 metal to ligand species could be determined in solution. In Ni(II)-AGN system thick white precipitate appeared between the pH

where the solution permitted calculation of the formation constant of only 1 : 1 metal to ligand species. In the metal-chelate system of Pb(II) with ADN and TGN the precipitations were observed from the pH of complex formation, but in the present system it was possible to evaluate the formation constants

of 1:1 species. The turbidity appeared at $pH \approx 6.9$.

The Mn(II), Co(II) and Zn(II) chelate systems precipitated at $pH \approx 7.55$, 6.6 and 6.4 respectively, and the formation functions could not be evaluated. Ca(II) and Mg(II) did not show any tendency of chelate formation with AGN. Thus the chelation reactions of AGN appears quite similar to ADN and TGN with the metal ions chosen for the study.

Since, in the cancer cell the abnormal cell growth may be due to the complexation of the abnormal or the carcinogenic metal ions with the enzyme of nucleic acid systems and the anticancer drugs may check the carcinogenesis binding the abnormal metal ions or the nucleic acids via transition metal ions⁴⁻⁸, the existence of the Ni(II), Be(II) and Al(III) AGN chelate equilibria at biological pH 7.3 shows that AGN can deactivate the carcinogenesis, binding the abnormal metal ions or the nucleic acids. Anti-cancer effects of AGN in the carcinogenesis due to the metal ions, Cu(II), $UO_2(VI)$, Pb(II), Cr(III), and Co(II) is possible if their precipitate remains in the form of complex species with AGN.

The order of stabilities of AGN chelates is as under :

Comparing the stabilities of purine and its derivatives, e.g. purine (PRN), TGN, ADN, 6-mercaptopurine (6 MP) it appears that :

The above relations of stability constants may explain the effects of AGN as a strong anticancer agent.

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